

Exteriorization and Intraperitoneal Closure of Uterus in Caesarean Delivery: A Comparative Study

Manjula A. Patil¹, Vindhyashree S.²

¹Associate Professor, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Adichunchangiri Institute of Medical Sciences, Mandya, Karnataka, India.

²Senior Resident, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Adichunchangiri Institute of Medical Sciences, Mandya, Karnataka, India.

Received: 21-11-2022 / Revised: 21-12-2022 / Accepted: 20-01-2023

Corresponding author: Dr. Vindhyashree S.

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Background: Caesarean delivery is the most common intraperitoneal surgical procedure in obstetrics. Many surgical techniques for caesarean delivery have been described, and the debate about the ideal caesarean technique to minimize morbidity is going on still.

Aim: To assess the intraoperative and postoperative advantages and disadvantages following exteriorization of uterus at caesarean section with intraperitoneal repair of uterus.

Methods: It is a RCT conducted at Adichunchangiri Institute of Medical Sciences, B G Nagar, Mandya. Minimum of 100 cases, 50 each were randomly allocated into exteriorized and in situ groups. All patients who were undergoing emergency and elective caesarean delivery under spinal anaesthesia were randomly allocated into Exteriorization and intraperitoneal group. In exteriorization group, uterus is exteriorized after delivery of foetus and placenta for repair, whereas in intraperitoneal group in situ repair was done. A pfannenstiel incision was taken for all the cases. Placenta was removed either by controlled traction after spontaneous separation or manually. Uterus was exteriorized after delivery of placenta and may be repaired by single or double layer. Visceral and parietal peritoneum are not closed.

Results: There is significant difference in the operating time in the exteriorization group and in the in situ group. But no significant difference between 2 groups regarding nausea, vomiting intra operatively, in return of bowel function, number of analgesic doses, incidence of cystitis, endometritis and wound infection. Period of hospitalization were also same in both groups.

Conclusions: Exteriorization of uterus at caesarean delivery has the advantages less perioperative haemoglobin reduction, good exposure, good access to incision angle, specially during difficult extraction. Easy identification of uterine anomaly, adnexal mass if present and exposure of posterior aspect of lower segment.

Keywords: Exteriorization, Intraperitoneal Closure, Caesarean Delivery, Exposure.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Background

Caesarean delivery is the most common intraperitoneal surgical procedure in obstetrics. Though over the year there is a

wider recognition of desire to reduce caesarean section rate, there has being little debate on operating technique. [1-4] Various studies on the technique of

performing caesarean focussed on reducing blood loss, operating time, wound infection and improved effective facilities made caesarean delivery safer than before. [5,6] The incidence varies worldwide between 3 to 31%. In England in 2003-2004, 23% of all the babies were born by caesarean delivery, which was an increase from 15% in 1993-1994. [1] Similar trends are seen in figures from the United States (31% in 2006) and Australia (29% in 2004). [1]

It is the most commonly performed operations in obstetrics, the obstetrician should be used to the procedures and as well know about the recent innovations of techniques. Many surgical techniques for caesarean delivery have been described, and the debate about the ideal caesarean technique to minimize morbidity is going on still. [1,7] According to ACOG 2000 guidelines the highest variation occurs among nulliparous women with term singleton fetuses with cephalic presentation and without other complications. High risk patients have much lower variations in caesarean delivery rates between practitioners and hospitals. [1]

Keeping this in mind, we performed the present study with aim of comparing the differences, merits and demerits between exteriorization and intraperitoneal repair of uterus regarding rate of nausea, intraoperative blood loss, duration of surgery, analgesics required during postoperative period, length of hospital stay and surgical site infection.

Aims and Objectives

To assess the intraoperative and postoperative advantages and disadvantages following exteriorization of uterus at caesarean section with intraperitoneal repair of uterus.

Methods

It is a randomized controlled trial conducted at Adichunchanagiri Institute of

Medical Sciences, B G Nagar, Mandya for one year

Inclusion Criteria

All cases of Caesarean delivery with gestational age > 28 weeks. Primary or repeat caesarean section.

Exclusion Criteria

- Classical caesarean delivery Vertical incision of the skin.
- Inverted T incision on the uterus.
- Previous abdominal surgeries
- Caesarean section done under General Anaesthesia
- Chorioamnionitis

100 cases were included in the study, out of which 50 cases each were randomly allocated into exteriorised group (case) and insitu repair (control) groups.

Procedure

All patients who were undergoing emergency and elective caesarean delivery under spinal anaesthesia were randomly allocated into Exteriorization and intraperitoneal uterine closure group. In exteriorization group, uterus is exteriorized after delivery of foetus and placenta for repair, whereas in intraperitoneal closure group, in situ repair was done.

A pfannenstiel incision was taken for all the cases. Placenta was removed either by controlled traction after spontaneous separation or manually. Uterus was exteriorized after delivery of placenta and repaired either by single or double layer closure. Visceral and parietal peritoneum are not closed. Rectus sheath is approximated by delayed absorbable sutures. Skin approximated with subcuticular or mattress suture.

Results

Comparison of two groups done by Z test and students t test for continuous data and chi square test for categorical data. There is significant difference in the operating

time in the exteriorization group(case) and in the in situ(control) group. But no significant difference between 2 groups regarding nausea, vomiting intra operatively, resumption of bowel function, number of analgesic doses, incidence of cystitis, endometritis and wound infection. Period of hospitalization were also same in both groups. There is no significant difference in two groups with respect to age and parity.

Out of 50, 46 were term patients, 3 were preterm and one was post term in exteriorized (case) group. Among 50 insitu(control) group 49 were term and 1 was preterm. Majority of the caesarean delivery were done on term patients in both the groups. There was not much significant difference between the groups regarding Gestational age.

Figure 1: Comparison of Gestational Age

Among 50 cases and controls 48 were emergency in exteriorised group and 44 were insitu in study group. No significant difference between the groups with respect to type of delivery. Majority of the exteriorised (case) and insitu (control) group caesarean sections were emergency.

Figure 2: Comparison of Elective Versus Emergency Caesarean Delivery

There is no significant difference in respect to indications for caesarean section. Maximum indications is for foetal distress and CPD and one case of twin gestation underwent caesarean in study group. The indications for LSCS didn't affect the study.

Figure 3: Comparison of Indications for Caesarean Delivery

The febrile morbidity is taken into consideration if the patient develops fever of 100⁰F. After 24 hrs. of LSCS. No much differences observed in exteriorised (case) and insitu (control) group regarding Febrile Morbidity.

Figure 4: Comparison of Febrile Morbidity

Out of 50 cases only three patient had intraoperative nausea and vomiting. No differences in intraoperative nausea or vomiting in both the groups.

Figure 5: Comparison of Intraoperative Nausea or Vomiting

Discussion

The technique of uterine exteriorization remains controversial. Exteriorization of uterus facilitates repair of uterine incision by not only improving access, but also reduces blood loss by compression of uterine vessels; sometimes it is believed that it causes intraoperative haemodynamic instability, postoperative pain, puerperal pyrexia, UTI, wound infection, increased blood loss and embolism.

The first comparative study by Hershey and Quilligan [8] in 1978 reported higher vomiting in the exteriorization group and a higher mean haematocrit drop in those who had in situ repair.

Wahab (1999) in a randomized, controlled study of uterine exteriorization and repair in caesarean section found that with effective anaesthesia there will be no significant problems and is associated with less blood loss [9]. Our study results also shows less blood loss in exteriorised group in comparison with intraperitoneal group.

Sood (2003) in his randomized controlled study to assess intraoperative and postoperative morbidity following exteriorization of uterus compared to insitu repair of the uterus found that there were significant reductions in intraoperative blood loss and perioperative haemoglobin decrease in study group in comparison with the control group. There was no significant difference in operating time, postoperative analgesic doses and incidence of cystitis, endomyometritis, wound infection and hospital stay period. [10]

Magann and Dodson in their prospective randomised study involving 100 women who were undergoing caesarean section, compared blood loss in the exteriorized versus non exteriorized groups, with manual versus spontaneous placental removal subgroups and reported that uterine position did not significantly affect blood loss in the spontaneous group or

manual removal groups, but the method. [11]

In a Cochrane review by Wilkinson and Enkin (2000) two trials involving 486 women included. Exteriorization had no significant blood loss and postoperative infections, nausea and vomiting. They drew a conclusion of insufficient information and needs further evaluation to use exteriorization as a routine technique. [12]

Conclusions

Exteriorization of uterus has more advantages. The incision and bleeding points are visualized more quickly and are amenable for easy repair because of good exposure, especially if there are any uterine angle extensions laterally or vertical lower segment tears extending downwards during difficult extraction of the baby. The tone of the uterus can be easily looked for and atonic uterus can be recognised quickly and compression given. Adnexal exposure is superior and tubal ligation is easier. The other merit of exteriorization of uterus is that the anatomical defect of the uterus and any adnexal mass if present can be well made out which can be easily missed through in situ repair. Another thing to be noted is lesser perioperative haemoglobin reduction among exteriorized group compared to intraperitoneal closure group.

References

1. Cunningham FG et al. Caesarean delivery and postpartum hysterectomy. Textbook of Williams Obstetrics, 23rd edition. New York; McGraw Hill 2001: 538-559.
2. Quilligan EJ, Wharton TJ. Clinical obstetrics and Gynecology. 1985;24(4).
3. Arulkumaran S, Ratnam SS. Caesarean deliveries changing trends. The management of labour. K. Bhaskar Rao Editor, Orient Longman, 2001: 308.
4. Dutta DK, Dutta B. History of caesarean delivery. In: textbook of

- caesarean delivery. A FOGSI Publications, New Delhi; Jaypee Brothers: 1-3.
5. Kumar SAA. Exteriorization of uterus at caesarean section. *J Obstet Gynecol India* 2003;53(4):353-358
 6. Renu Mishra. Ian Donald Practical obstetric problem. 5th ed. Caesarean section. New Delhi; BI publication Pvt.Ltd., 1998:827-838.
 7. Arulkumaran S, Ratnam SS. Operative delivery. The management of labour. Donald MF Gibb editor, Orient Longman, 2001:137.
 8. Hershey DW, Quilligan EJ. Extra abdominal uterine exteriorization at caesarean section. *Obstetric Gynecol* 1978; 52:189-92.
 9. Wahab MA, Karantzis P, Eccerley PS, Russell IF, Thompson JW, Lindow SW. A randomised controlled study of uterine exteriorization and repair at caesarean section. *Br J Obstet and Gynecol* 1999; 106:913-916.
 10. Sood AK. Exteriorization of uterus at Cesarean section. *Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology of India*, 53(4):353-358.
 11. Magann EF et al. Blood loss at the time of caesarean section by method of placental removal and exteriorization versus in situ repair of the uterine incision. *Surg Gynecol Obstet* 1993; 177:389-392.
 12. Wilkinson C, Enkin MW. Uterine exteriorization versus intraperitoneal repair at caesarean section. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev* 2000;2:CD000085.